

DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF INJECTION-MOLDED GLASS FIBER / POLYAMIDE 66 COMPOSITES WITH HIGH VOLUME FRACTION OF GLASS FIBERS

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Keywords: Material testing, Fractography, Composite material, Tensile and fracture properties, Fastening products

ABSTRACT

This paper presents experimental results for the deformation and fracture properties of injection-molded glass fiber/polyamide 66 composites. A weighed amount of glass fibers was mixed with polyamide 66 using a twin extruder and the amount of glass fibers was varied from 17 to 41 vol%. Tensile tests were performed on flat tensile (FT) specimens and three point bending tests were carried out on single-edge notched bend (SENB) specimens. Specimens were prepared by cutting injection-molded plates in three different directions: parallel to the flow direction (0°-FT and 0°-SENB specimens), normal to the flow direction (90°-FT and 90°-SENB specimens), and 45° to the flow direction (45°-FT and 45°-SENB specimens). Injection-molded FT and SENB specimens (M-FT and M-SENB specimens) were also used. The effects of the specimen orientation and fiber volume fraction on the tensile and fracture properties were investigated. In addition, the microstructure of the fracture surfaces of the composites was examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The Young's modulus increased as the fiber volume fraction was increased from 17 to 41 vol%, but the maximum tensile strength was achieved at a fiber volume fraction of 27 vol%. For the same fiber volume fraction, the Young's modulus and tensile strength of the 0°-FT specimen were higher than those of the 45°- and 90°-FT specimens. Moreover, the strain energy at the maximum load for the SENB specimens remained nearly constant at the fiber volume fraction was increased.

1 INTRODUCTION

Because of light weight and attractive mechanical properties, glass fiber/polyamide 66 composites are potential materials for fastening products. Images of a fastening product are shown in Figure 1. However, very limited information has been reported for injection-molded glass fiber/polyamide 66 composites with a high volume fraction of glass fibers which are potentially suitable for fastening products.

Various approaches and methods have been used to study the deformation and fracture behavior of different types of molded composite materials. It is commonly known that molded composite materials have layers with different fiber orientations which affect their melt flow behavior. Hourst and Spoomaker reported molded composite materials consisting of three layers (skin-core-skin) with different fiber orientations [1]. Recently, the formation of skin and core layers in composite materials has been predicted by analysis of the flow-front behavior of melted composites by the finite element method [2-3]. Moreover, Yokoi and Matsuda observed the moment of formation of a layer with different fiber orientations using a visualized mold [4]. Sankaran and mallick investigated the effect of injection molding conditions on the fatigue behavior of 18vol% glass fiber/polyamide 66 composites including the

skin and core layers [5]. Hourst and Spoomaker also used a similar approach to investigate 17 vol% glass fiber/ polyamide 6 composites [1]. In addition, Mutou et al. reported that the skin layer has a critical effect on the tensile properties (Young's modulus and tensile strength) [6]. On the other hand, the fracture toughness of glass fiber reinforced composites has also been extensively reported. Yilmaz and Yilmaz discussed the effect of the fiber volume fraction on the fracture toughness of glass fiber/ polyamide 6 composites their results showed that increasing the fiber volume fraction increases the maximum load and decreases the strain energy [7]. He et al. carried out fracture toughness tests on double-edged notched tension specimens and investigated the effect of the ligament length and fiber orientation on the fracture properties of 10 vol% glass fiber/polyethylene composites [8].

The aim of this work is to investigate the tensile and fracture properties of glass fiber/polyamide 66 composites with various fiber volume fractions and fiber orientations. Tensile tests were performed on flat tensile (FT) specimens and three point bending tests were carried out on single-edge notched bend (SENB) specimens. The effects of the specimen orientation and fiber volume fraction on the deformation and fracture properties of the composites were investigated. In addition, the microstructure of the fracture surfaces of the composites was examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Fig.1 Images of fastening product

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials and specimens

The polyamide 66 (Leona 1300S) used as a matrix material in this study was a commercial product, supplied in pellet form by Asahikasei Chemicals Company, Japan. The chopped glass fibers (CS3J459) used as a reinforcing material, which had 11 μ m diameter and 3mm length, were also a commercial product supplied by Nittobo Company, Japan. The densities of the polyamide 66 and glass fibers were 1.2g/cm³ and 2.6g/cm³, respectively.

The geometry of the tensile specimens is illustrated in Figure 2. The geometry was in accordance with the specifications outlined in ISO572-2 [9]. Specimens were prepared by cutting injection-molded plates in three different directions: parallel to the flow direction (0°-FT and 0°-SENB specimens), normal to the flow direction (90°-FT and 90°-SENB specimens), and 45° to the flow direction (45°-FT and 45°-SENB specimens). Injection-molded FT and SENB specimens (M-FT and M-SENB specimens) were also used. The dimensions of the injection-molded plates and the specimen cutting direction are shown in Figure 3, and the layout of the injection-molded M-FT specimens is shown in Figure 4. The geometry of the specimens used in the fracture toughness test is illustrated in Figure 5. The fracture toughness test was carried out on SENB specimens prepared from the straight parts of FT specimens (M-SENB, 0°-SENB, 45°-SENB, and 90°-SENB specimens). Where the notch was made using a cutter with chevron shape. Each injection-molded plate had a gate of 1mm thickness between the runner part and the product part where as the dumbbell shaped die did not have a gate. Generally, a gate is used to ensure easy separation of a product from a runner when the die is opened. The gate results in microstructure layers with different fiber orientations, because it has a significant effect on the melt viscosity of the composites which affects the fiber orientation. The arrows in Figures 3 and 4 show the flow directions of the melted composites. Table 1 gives conditions of injection molding.

Fig.2 Geometry of specimens used for tensile tests (dimensions in mm)

Fig.3 Dimensions of injection-molded plates and specimen cutting directions (dimensions in mm)

Fig.4 Layout of injection-molded M-FT specimens

Fig.5 Geometry of specimens used for fracture toughness tests (dimensions in mm)

Table 1 Conditions of injection molding

Molding Machine	FNX140 (clamp capacity 140t)
Desiccating condition	80°C/12h (in a vacuum)
Melt Temperature	280-300°C
Mold Temperature	120-140°C
Injection Speed	40mm/s
Holding Pressure	50MPa

2.2 Tensile test method

Tensile tests were performed at room temperature using a universal testing machine (Instron 55R-4206) in accordance with ISO527-2 [9] at a cross-head speed of 5mm/min. The stress was calculated by dividing the load by the original cross section. The displacement was measured using a contact extensometer (Instron 2620-601). The strain was calculated from the length of narrow section and displacement. The Young's modulus and tensile strength were evaluated from stress-strain data.

2.3 Fracture toughness test method

Fracture toughness tests were performed at room temperature using the same universal testing machine (Instron 55R-4206) in accordance with ASTM E1820-1 [10] at a cross-head speed of 0.3mm/min. The elastic and plastic parts of the area separated from the strain energy at the maximum load are shown in Figure 6. The displacement of specimens was defined on the basis of the cross-head displacement.

Fig.6 Definition of the area separated with elastic and plastic parts

2.4 Fractography observations

SEM examination was carried out on the fracture surfaces of specimens subjected to tensile and fracture toughness tests. Specimens were sputtered with a platinum coating by a Hitachi E102 Ion Sputter surface coating machine and were viewed with a Hitachi S-3400N SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile properties

Figure 7 shows the Young's modulus of the FT specimens with various fiber volume fractions and fiber orientations. As the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 41 vol%, the Young's modulus of each specimen increased. The Young's modulus of the 0°-FT specimens was larger than that of the other FT specimens. Likewise, the Young's modulus of the M-FT specimens was largest in this test. Figure 8 shows the tensile strength of the FT specimens with various fiber volume fractions and fiber orientations. As the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 27 vol%, the tensile strength of all the FT specimens increased. However, as the fiber volume fraction increased from 27 to 41 vol%, the tensile strength of the 0°, 45°, and 90°-FT specimens decreased. In contrast, the tensile strength of the M-FT specimens increased steadily with the increasing fiber volume fraction. The tensile strength of the 0°-FT specimens was slightly higher than that of the 90°-FT and 45°-FT specimens. This is attributed to the greater number of glass fibers parallel to the tensile direction [4-6]. Similarly, the number of glass fibers parallel to the tensile direction in the M-FT specimens was greater than that in the other FT specimens.

Figures 9 and 10 respectively show, SEM images of the fracture surfaces of the 0°-FT specimens with 17 and 41 vol% glass fiber after the tensile test. Each specimen had a core layer with a fiber orientation perpendicular to the tensile direction and a skin layer with a fiber orientation parallel to the tensile direction. The fracture surface of the skin layer featured some holes generated by the pulling out fibers as well as fibers protruding from the fracture surface. The core layer of the 0°-FT specimen with 41 vol% glass fibers was thicker than the core layer of the 0°-FT specimen with 17 vol% glass fibers. (The widths of the core layers of the 0°-FT specimens with 41, 27, and 17 vol% glass fibers were 1.6, 1.2, and 0.5mm, respectively). As the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 41 vol%, the width of the core layer increased. Figure 11 shows SEM images of the fracture surface of the M-FT specimen with 41 vol% glass fibers after the tensile test. The fracture surface of the M-FT specimen exhibited hardly any core layer. Therefore, the core layer was considerably affected by the gate in the mold and the viscosity of the composite which was dependent on the fiber volume fraction.

Fig.7 Effect of fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation on the Young's modulus of FT specimens

Fig.8 effect of fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation on the tensile strength of FT specimens

Fig.9 Fracture surfaces of 0°-FT specimen with 17 vol% glass fibers: (a) image of skin and core layers; (b) high-magnification image of skin layer; (c) high-magnification image of core layer

Fig.10 Fracture surfaces of 0°-FT specimen with 41 vol% glass fibers: (a) image of skin and core layers; (b) high-magnification image of skin layer; (c) high-magnification image of core layer

Fig.11 Fracture surfaces of M-FT specimen with 41vol% glass fibers: (a) image of skin and core layers; (b) high-magnification image of skin layer; (c) high-magnification image of core layer

3.2 Fracture toughness properties

Figure 12 shows the strain energy at the maximum load in the three point bending test of the SENB specimens with various fiber volume fractions and fiber orientations. The strain energy of the SENB specimens at the maximum load remained nearly constant as the fiber volume fraction increased. However, as the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 41 vol%, the plastic part of the strain energy increased slightly. In addition, the maximum strain energy was achieved for the 45° SENB specimens. The elastic part of the strain energy of the M-SENB specimen with 41 vol% glass fibers was approximately 1.5 times greater than that of the other specimens. This may be due to the number of fibers parallel to the longitudinal direction of the specimen, a consequence of fiber breakage was affected by the fiber orientation.

Figure 13 shows SEM images of the fracture surface of the 0°-SENB specimen with 27 vol% glass fibers after the fracture toughness test. Hardly any holes generated by the pulling out of fibers were observed and fiber breakage was observed on the fracture surface of the 0°-SENB specimen with 27 vol% glass fibers. Moreover, plastic deformation around the fibers was apparent. The increase in the plastic part of the strain energy as the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 41 vol% is considered to be due to plastic deformation around the fibers. Moreover, the large elastic part of strain energy for the M-SENB specimen with 41 vol% glass fibers was due to the large number of fibers parallel to the longitudinal direction of the specimen. As a consequence, the fiber breakage was affected by the fiber orientation.

Fig.12 Effect of fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation on the strain energy at the maximum load for the SENB specimens

Fig.13 Fracture surfaces of 0°-SENB specimen with 27 vol% glass fibers: (a) image of skin and core layers; (b) high-magnification image of skin layer; (c) high-magnification image of core layer

4 CONCLUSIONS

The tensile and fracture properties of glass fiber/polyamide 66 composites with various fiber volume fractions and fiber orientations were investigated. The tensile test was carried out on FT specimens and the fracture toughness test was carried out on SENB specimens. The results can be summarized as follows.

1. As the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 41 vol%, the Young's modulus of each specimen increased.
2. As the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 27 vol%, the tensile strength of all the FT specimen increased. However, as the fiber volume fraction increased from 27 to 41 vol%, the tensile strength of the 0°, 45°, and 90°-FT specimens decreased and the tensile strength of the M-FT specimens increased.
3. The strain energy at the maximum load for the SENB specimens remained nearly constant at the fiber volume fraction increased. However, as the fiber volume fraction increased from 17 to 41 vol%, the plastic part of the strain energy increased slightly.

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